

AFFIXOIDATION AS A PRODUCTIVE WAY OF WORD FORMATION IN MODERN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.

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ANNOTATION

The article is about affixoids, which are word-building elements that have some of the features of both affixes and word stems. One of the main features that usually belongs to affixes is their ability to produce new semantic and grammar categories. This is what affixoids do by helping to develop new words. Language users' actions, not automated, predictable processes, are what cause morphological change. They have an open structure. Successive successful reinterpretations may serve as the foundation for new derivations. When a process like that for forming derivative words starts. Additionally, this article demonstrates how language changes of the distinction between morphological categories and distinct morphological processes like compounding and derivation. Most of the examples are from English and Uzbek, but there are also a few words from other languages that are discussed.

Keywords: *language change, reinterpretation, bidirectionality, affixoid, prefiksoid, suffiksoid, derivation, word formation.*

Word formation is the main topic of this article. The topic of reinterpretation is covered morphological change could result from the use of opaque data. It also has that in addition demonstrates how language change erodes the distinction between distinct morphological procedures, including compounding and derivation, as well obscures the distinction between morphological categories.

There are four sections to the article, each of which is introduced in the preamble. This section will look at the differences between affix and affixoid in English and

Uzbek. The four components are as follows: introduction, affixoids in English, affixoids in Uzbek and conclusion. It may be useful to define the differences between affixes and affixoids.

In Uzbek, some words function as affixes, following morphemes even if it is approaching, it has not yet become an affix. All these are also known as **Affixoids**: qabulxona, choyxona, darsxona, ishxona, ruxsatnoma, talabnoma, tabriknoma. For example, “bu uyda to‘rt xona bor”- “biz ishxonada uchrashdik”. It seems that “Xona” is a word instead of a word is also used as an affix. It is a root morpheme in one place and a suffix in another comes as a morpheme: molxona, muzxona.²²

Affixes are abstractions and intellectual tendencies in linguistics. The introduction of new word streams, new meanings into the language in a very short period of time has led to major changes in the model of word formation increase in affix construction. The current research focuses on linguistic investigations aimed at elucidating affix phenomena in Romanian neologism mechanisms. Vocabulary creation corresponds to a universal dimension of the conscious creativity of the scientist and names the expertise increasingly used in specialized language.

This was an attempt to explain the phenomenon of affixing in the embryo by identifying sources for completing the affix inventory, including abbreviations, symbol names, letter names, eponyms, and Greek-Latin. It represents an intermediate connection between a root and an affix.

To determine the potential properties of an affix, Stevens proposes five criteria: paraphrased and summarized

- (a) Affixoids can participate productively in new formations;
- (b) Affixoids are formally identical and usually coexist with free "parent" morphs.
- (c) The meaning of an affix is more general and abstract than that of its parent morpheme.

²² Shoabdurahmonov Sh., Asqarova M., Hojiyev A. and others. "Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili". Part I. Tashkent: Uqituvchi, 1980.

(d) In the original morphogenesis that gave rise to the affix, two parts of the formation.

(e) Affix propagates in conflict with or in complement to affix.²³

The article looks at affixes that are used to create words that have a middle status. These affixes have both a suffix and a root. This research is important because it focuses on a problem that has not been studied extensively in linguistic literature- the affixoid in Uzbek. This is important because it will help to define the volume of the term “affixoid”, work out principles of classification and typology, and explore the possible semantic changes if affixoids are compared with independent root morphemes and component words in compound words.

The phrase "semi-affixation" was proposed by M.D Stepanova in the 1950s, root morphemes, which frequently take part in the word-formation process and maintain all formal and semantic ties to the corresponding, to the root. They:

- indicate, like affixes, a broad word-forming category: people, objects, such as characteristics;
- They produce a lot and frequently contribute to the development of new words.
- Can compete with "real" affixes when it comes to carrying out their main purpose.²⁴

In the 90s of the twentieth century, Yu. A. Zatsny also touched upon the problem of alternative word-building, using the term a “pseudo-compound” word.²⁵

Affixes are considered to be a component of words in Uzbek linguistics (“attached” in Latin), a morpheme used to create a word or grammatical expression in contrast to a root. As a result, it is separated into two categories: word generators and form generators. It appears at the start of the word (affix), in the middle of the word

²³ Stevens, Ch. (2005). Revisiting the affixoid debate: On the grammaticalization of the word. In T. Leuschner, T. Mortelmans, and S. De Groot, eds., *Grammatikalisierung im Deutschen*. Berlin/New York: Mouton de Gruyter, pp. 71–83.

²⁴ Stepanova M.D. (1953). “Slovoobrazovanie sovremennogo nemetskogo yazyka [Word-building of modern German]”. Moscow: Izdatel'stvo literatury na inostrannykh yazykakh. (in Russian)

²⁵ Zacyj Ju.A. (1999). “The development of English vocabulary in the 1980s and 1990s of the XXc, (PhD Thesis). Kyiv: Kyiv University named after T.H. Shevchenka.

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(infix), or at the end of the word (suffix), depending on where it is in relation to the root. Words are divided into root and formed words in the Uzbek language dictionary. For example: “paxta” - root word, but “paxtakor” - formed word.

There are mainly two ways of forming words in modern Uzbek:

- 1) affixation (or morphological) method;
- 2) composition (or syntactic) method;²⁶

Affixoids, they are also called word-affixes are rare in the Uzbek language.

“Ham-“ affixoid in the language, the adverb is used in the meaning of the word and work understood from the base, it forms a personal noun with the meaning of being related to something: hamshahar, hamsuhbat, hamkurs, hamkasb.²⁷ With what the base of this affixoid “noma” represents dependent letter and forms a noun with the meaning of a document: guvoh-noma, shart-noma, taklif-noma, baxt-noma, ayb-noma, tashakkur-noma, arz- noma.

This is what the base of affixoid “parvar” construction means, an attribute denoting a sign, condition, characteristic related to action makes: vatan-parvar, sulh-parvar, ma’rifat-parvar, taraqqiy- parvar.

The affixoid “bad” is the basis of making affixoid persons and things adjective indicating a negative sign related to the meaning: had-jahl, bad-bashara, bad-qovoq, bad-hazm, bad-fe’l, bad-nafs, bad-mast, bad-axloq.

Forms expressing the meaning of caressing are made with the affixes - jon, -xon. These are independent words in addition to declension, personal pronouns and related nouns also to express the meaning of joining, caressing. They are akajon, ukajon, xolajon, Hakimjon, Olimjon, Zohidjon, Asalxon, Zulfiyaxon, Lolaxon, Anorxon.

Affixoids in English. A first example from Marchand (1969: 211) will show how libfixing may work: English scape, landscape, seascape, mindscape, moonscape, soundscape, dreamscape, memoryscape.

²⁶ Rahmatullayev Sh. “Hozirgi adabiy o‘zbek tili”. I va II qismlar. Toshkent: Mumtoz so‘z, 2010.

²⁷ Jamolxonov H. Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili. T., 2005. 85 page.

Landscape is the opaque form by which English speakers recognize the existing word “land”²⁸. Subsequent reinterpretations have led to the analysis as if landscape was a compound word. So “scape” should be given a certain morphological status that it can be used productively like . Recent mint soundscapes, dreamscapes, and memoryscapes show that the process is still productive.

Another similar example offers forms derived from the English forms “watergate” and “hamburger”. Gate: watergate, closetgate, nipplegate, donutgate.

Burger: hamburger, cheeseburger, fishburger.

In summary, throughout this article, it is argued that there is an intermediate category between stems and affixes: the affixoid. Indeed, the process of affixing is a chronological process that interacts with the morphological system that accepts stems and affixes as inputs to word-forming processes, namely compounding and derivation. Modern word construction exhibits an affixoidation tendency; compound words are created using preexisting sentences and word combinations, but they are constructed using preexisting word-building patterns simply by adding root morphemes. These morphemes are thus peculiar and near to affixes.

As word-units of intermediate status, affixoids have the following significant qualities: productivity, the ability to express a specific lexical meaning, the potential to develop an abstract meaning, the ability to refer to an object as belonging to a particular class or subclass, and the capacity to be combined with various word-building components.

REFERENCES

1. *Shoabdurahmonov Sh., Asqarova M., Hojiyev A. and others. "Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili". Part I. Tashkent: Uqituvchi, 1980.*
2. *Stevens, Ch. (2005). Revisiting the affixoid debate: On the grammaticalization of the word. In T. Leuschner, T. Mortelmans, and S. De Groot, eds., Grammatikalisierung im Deutschen. Berlin/New York: Mouton de Gruyter, pp. 71–83.*

²⁸ Marchand, H. 1969. The categories and types of Present-Day English word-formation. München: Beck. 211-page

3. Stepanova M.D. (1953). “Slovoobrazovanie sovremennogo nemetskogo yazyka [Word-building of modern German]”. Moscow: Izdatel'stvo literatury na inostrannykh yazykakh. (in Russian)
4. Zacnyj Ju.A. (1999). “The development of English vocabulary in the 1980s and 1990s of the XXc, (PhD Thesis). Kyiv: Kyiv University named after T.H. Shevchenka. P 11.
5. Rahmatullayev Sh. “Hozirgi adabiy o'zbek tili”. I va II qismlar. Toshkent: Mumtoz so'z, 2010.
6. Jamolxonov H. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. T., 2005. P 85
7. Marchand, H. 1969. The categories and types of Present-Day English word-formation. Munchen: Beck. P 211